

ANEMIA DURING PREGNANCY

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Resume. Anemia is one of the most common eating disorders affecting pregnant women in developing countries. Anemia during pregnancy is usually associated with an unfavorable pregnancy outcome and can lead to life-threatening complications for both the mother and the fetus.

Key words: anemia, maternal morbidity, prevalence.

Anemia is one of the most common eating disorders affecting pregnant women; the prevalence in developed countries is 14%, in developing countries 51%, and in India it ranges from 65% to 75%.[1,2]

Anemia is the second most common cause of maternal mortality in India and accounts for about 80% of maternal deaths caused by anemia in Southeast Asia. [2,3,4,5] Anemia is also an established risk factor for intrauterine development delay. , which leads to deterioration of newborn health and perinatal death [6,7,8,9,10].

A prospective observational study is being conducted to assess the prevalence and study maternal and early neonatal morbidity and mortality associated with anemia in pregnant women.

Materials and methods. A prospective observational study was conducted in three primary health care centers (PHC) Kolar Taluka in the period from March 2013 to January 2015 The sample size of 446 pregnant women was estimated based on the prevalence of anemia among pregnant women at 59% (National Family Health Survey [NFHS]-3) with a confidence level of 95% and an absolute accuracy of 5%, including a dropout rate of 20%.

A multi-stage sampling method was used to select a pregnant woman. Randomly selected three PHCPS and accredited Social Health Activists (ASHA), employees of these PHCPS, were trained and motivated to deliver all selected cases of prenatal care to the prenatal consultation for PHC on set days. The pregnant woman was examined by an OBG consultant, and graduate students and data were collected. A pre-tested and semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data; the woman was monitored every month with the help of an ASHA employee up to 1 week after giving birth. The hemoglobin (HB) of pregnant women was measured at the first visit and repeated every 3 months. The HB measurements of a pregnant woman were carried out using a HemoCue analyzer (HemoCue Hb 301). Anemia was classified based on WHO criteria; HB concentration <11 g/dl was regarded as anemia HB concentrations of 10-10.9

g/dl, 7-9.9 g/dl and <7 g/dl were considered as mild, moderate and severe anemia, respectively.

Pregnant women were consulted about their hemoglobin levels and the importance of consuming iron and folic acid tablets, local iron-rich foods, regular prenatal checkups, etc.

Quantitative indicators are represented by the mean and standard deviation, and qualitative variables are represented by proportions. Chi-squared test, correlation coefficient and logistic regression were used to test significance. $P \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. The results obtained. A total of 446 pregnant women were included in the study, who were followed up to the 1st week after childbirth. Of the 446 women included, 427 women completed follow-up with a dropout rate of 9.5%. The average age of pregnant women was 23 years. Most of the women were Hindus belonging to castes (SC)/tribes (ST) (57.4%) and living below the poverty line (89%). The prevalence of anemia among pregnant women was 62.3%, and it was noted that anemia was common in the age group of 21-30 years (66.1%), SC/ST (61.6%) and OBC (30.8%). A significant relationship between the status of anemia and educational status and pregnancy was revealed. The prevalence of anemia increased with increasing gestation, but was not statistically significant. Anemia is more common in women with an interval between childbirth < 1 year (40.2%).

Conclusion. The high prevalence of anemia among pregnant women (63%) indicates that anemia continues to be a serious public health problem in rural India. Anemia during pregnancy increases the risk to the mother and fetus. Pregnancy status, women's literacy and poor obstetric history were important risk factors for anemia in pregnant women. To improve maternal and fetal outcomes, it is recommended to strengthen primary health care and prioritize aspects such as prevention, early diagnosis and treatment of anemia during pregnancy.

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